

Solution Stability Constants of Transition Metal Complexes with 4-Methoxy Salicylaldehyde

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In our present investigation the potentiometric method for the determination of the stability constants has been used. The metals chosen for the purpose have closely spaced electro-negativity values. It has been found from the literature that the work on salicylaldehyde and substituted salicylaldehyde has been done for very few metals by some workers^{3-10,14} in the past. Calvin and Wilson¹⁰ have done the work with metals like copper with substituted salicylaldehyde, substituents being in various positions of the benzene ring. The present work is restricted to the metals Mg^{++} , Mn^{++} , Fe^{++} , Co^{++} , Ni^{++} , Cu^{++} , Zn^{++} and Cd^{++} .

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental method used is identical with that of Calvin and Wilson¹⁰. The ligand being water insoluble, a mixed solvent, 75% dioxane-25% water (v/v), is used. 0.1M sodium perchlorate solution was used to maintain constant ionic strength. Temperature during the titration sets was maintained at 30°, by means of water circulating thermostat.

'Elico' pH-meter Model LI-10 with Beckmann glass electrode and saturated calomel electrode assembly has been employed. The ligand, 4-methoxy salicylaldehyde, prepared in the laboratory and analysed for its purity was found to be a very pure sample. Dioxane was purified by the standard method given by Vogel.

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Titration sets consisted of the following:—

1. 5ml MClO_4 + 5 ml NaClO_4 + 30 ml dioxane.
2. 5 ml MClO_4 + 5 ml NaClO_4 + 5 ml ligand + 25 ml dioxane.
3. 5 ml MClO_4 + 5 ml NaClO_4 + 5 ml ligand + 25 ml dioxane.

MClO_4 represents the metal perchlorate.

Titrations were carried out in an inert atmosphere by bubbling oxygen free nitrogen, pressaturated with the mixed solvent, in the reaction cell.

Plots of B/V gave the values required in the further calculations. The procedure adopted for the calculations is similar to that of Irving and Rossotti¹⁵. From the titration curves in sets 1 and 2, the values of proton-ligand has been calculated. Sets 2 and 3 were used in the determination of the metal-ligand stability for the metals used.

DISCUSSION

By virtue of the low metal ion and ligand concentration, the metal complexes are not hydrolysed even at high pH values.

The proton-ligand value obtained for 4-methoxy salicylaldehyde in the present work $\log pK_1^H$ is 9.815, while that reported in the literature¹⁶ is 10.17. The difference in these two values is attributed to the different experimental conditions employed in the two investigations. Calvin and Wilson¹⁰ who reported the value to be 9.60 have studied it at 20° and in 50% dioxane-50% water mixture.

Values of $\bar{n}$ and pL were calculated and are plotted in Fig. 1. From this graph the values of successive stability constants are determined. The results obtained for metal-ligand stability are summarized in Table I.

TABLE I

Metal ion.	Atomic number	2nd Ionisation potential	Electronegativity ^{17,18}	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta_2$
Mg	12	14.96	1.23	3.29	—	—
Mn	25	15.70	1.60	3.98	(3.10)	7.08
Fe	26	16.16	1.64	4.30	3.25	7.55
Co	27	17.30	1.70	4.97	(2.58)	7.55
Ni	28	18.20	1.75	5.05	2.65	7.70
Cu	29	20.34	1.75	8.28	3.28	11.56
Zn	30	17.83	1.66	6.48	5.90	12.38
Cd	48	16.84	1.46	6.85	5.33	12.18

The results clearly indicate the relation between the electronegativity of the bivalent metal ions and the order of the stability, viz., $\text{Mg} < \text{Mn} < \text{Fe} < \text{Co} < \text{Ni} < \text{Cu} > \text{Zn} < \text{Cd}$. With the exception of cadmium, the order agrees with the one given by Mellor and Maley¹, A. Albert¹¹, and others^{11,12}. In the case of cadmium which should come between Iron(II)

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and Cobalt(II), a considerable deviation from the expected trend has been observed. In this case one can say that the forces involved in the complex formation may not be similar to those in the other cases. Here the formation of the complex may be stronger¹⁵ as compared with iron and cobalt, nickel and zinc. The overall stability, $\log \beta_n$, shows the same trend as that shown by the $\log K_1$ values. In this case the order comes to be $Mn < Fe = Co < Ni < Cu$. The complexes of zinc and cadmium here too do not obey the order. They have the values Cd: 12.18 and Zn: 12.38. Finally the order may be written as $Mn < Fe = Co < Ni < Cu > Zn > Cd$. Magnesium does not come in picture as it does not show any formation of 1 : 2 complex.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

Figure 2 indicates the relation between $\log K_n$ values and the second ionisation potential of the metal ion. Calvin and Melchoir¹⁷ attempted to explain the phenomenon by comparing a number of physical properties of ions under consideration, such as the ionic radius, heat of ionisation, partial molal entropy, and the ionisation potentials. The only obvious correlation was between stability and the second ionisation potential of the elements, as had been previously pointed out by Irving and Williams⁸. The authors pointed out that except for zinc this potential measures the energy required for the removal of a d-electron, and they suggested that coordination replaces this electron, so that, in each case, except zinc, the hybridisation should involve d-orbitals. The ionisation potential of a metal is only one factor influencing the stability of its complexes, and even if it is the controlling factor in the series of metals under consideration, it is not necessary to assume that on formation of ionic bond of the type existing in complexes one of the electrons must occupy the d-orbitals left vacant on ionisation of the metal. Hence there is no reason to postulate that the bonds existing in the complexes must involve hybridisation including d-orbitals.